

Relevance of Traditional Medicine in 21st Century: A study on South Mizoram with reference to CADC

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The 21st century has seen ever enhancing and advancement in medical sciences worldwide. Yet, traditional medicinal knowledge and health practices among the Chakmas in reference to the inhabitants of Chakma Autonomous District Council (CADC) has been a thriving need specially in rural areas. Various reasons attribute to this factor ranging from socio-cultural to economic backgrounds of the demographic region mostly due to constraints availability of proper medical health facilities. The practice involves the usages of *bonoja daru* (wild medicinal plants locally available) with *pajari daru* (non-local medicines) and incantation. Irrespective of the need, traditional medicinal knowledge and health practices have proved to be benevolently effective, limiting to some exceptional cases. This paper intends to study the flourishing (in rural areas) and surviving (in urban areas) usages of traditional medicinal knowledge among the Chakmas in present day CADC of Mizoram.

Keywords : Chakma, Traditional Medicine, Mizoram, CADC.